

Fusing user's intention and environment information in BMI driven robotic devices

Piero Simonetto¹, Stefano Tortora^{1,2}, Emanuele Menegatti^{1,2}, Luca Tonin^{1,2}

¹Department of Information Engineering, University of Padua, Italy

²Padova Neuroscience Center, University of Padua, Italy

Abstract—This paper provides an overview of current research in human-machine collaboration utilizing brain-machine interfaces (BMIs) within the IAS Lab at the University of Padua. BMIs are systems capable of translating human brain patterns into commands for robotic devices. However, thus far, research has not yielded a solution suitable for everyday end-user applications. Many existing approaches treat BMIs solely as decoding tools, by fully neglecting the robot intelligence. The IAS Laboratory takes a pioneering approach, redefining the conventional paradigm by assigning equal significance to the user's intention (via BMI) and robot intelligence. These entities can produce interdependent signals and mutually enhance each other's capabilities. By amalgamating neuroscientific and robotic methodologies, the primary objective is to establish and explicitly prioritize human-robot interaction, with the user at the core of the research focus

Index Terms—brain-machine interface, human-robot interaction, neurorobotics

I. INTRODUCTION

The capability to decode user intentions directly from brain signals presents the opportunity to employ brain-machine interfaces (BMIs) as seamless tools for integrating humans into the control loop of robotic devices [1], [2]. In traditional human-robot interaction paradigms, user input necessitates a physical action, such as pressing a button or issuing a voice command, resulting in inherent delays, particularly for individuals with severe motor disabilities.

Conversely, the introduction of a BMI device offers an alternative interface for individuals to interact with robots [3]. The integration of humans and robots through BMIs also holds promise for enhancing the independence of patients with disabilities [4], [5]. While this concept has been extensively explored in the literature, the realization of commercial devices that can bring these possibilities into people's homes has not yet materialized.

The predominant challenge within BMI-driven devices lies in the reliability of decoding user intentions from neural signals [6]. Neural signals inherently manifest non-stationarity, yielding substantial day-to-day performance fluctuations. This inherent variability represents a formidable impediment to the attainment of dependable BMI control.

This study was carried out within the PNRR research activities of the consortium iNEST (Interconnected North-East Innovation Ecosystem) funded by the European Union Next-GenerationEU (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) – Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – D.D. 1058 23/06/2022, *ECS_00000043*). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Fig. 1. Example of a wheelchair that can be controlled by the brain signals.

The secondary concern is related to the consequence of a learning phase done in front of a screen. Current approaches neglect how the real scenario influences the user's brain signal, reducing the generalizability of the BMI system [7]. Consequently, BMI-driven robotic devices lack the required readiness for real-world deployment.

Finally, current paradigms consider humans and robots as independent entities of information. This results in BMI decoders lacking of the contextual inputs gathered from robotic sensors. As a corollary, disparities may surface between the decoded intentions of the operator and the ensuing robotic actions, thereby impeding effective device control. This compartmentalized perspective diminishes the feasibility of human-robot collaboration via BMI, rendering the development of fully functional everyday-use products a formidable challenge [8].

II. PROJECT OVERVIEW

The primary aim of this project is to mitigate the limitations outlined in the introduction by establishing parity between the user and the robot. This objective will be realized through the development of a BMI decoder that integrates information from the robot's perception, thereby enabling contextualization of heterogenous data from robot and BMI. We expect that this integration will foster a closer coupling between the user and the robot, resulting in enhanced system reliability and robustness.

Fig. 2. The proposed robot control loop with BMI

To fulfill this goal, we have delineated three distinct objectives. These objectives will be investigated within the framework of an experimental setup centered around a brain-powered wheelchair, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

A. Objective O1: human-robot decoder

This objective grounds on the assumption that users' decisions are intrinsically influenced by their environmental context. Our aim is to seamlessly integrate environmental data directly into the BMI decoder, amalgamating the brain signal (electroencephalography) with contextual information, as elaborated in the second objective. To accomplish this, we will meticulously review the decoder training session to harmonize with real-world scenarios, thus augmenting users' readiness for practical tasks. Of importance is our exclusive reliance on data sourced from robot sensors, ensuring adaptability across diverse situational contexts. Our pursuit will involve an exploration of cutting-edge methodologies to craft a versatile controller with the capacity to accommodate heterogeneous data.

B. Objective O2: robot perception

In O1, we hypothesized that the robot could generate a signal compatible with the decoder. This objective seeks to emancipate from this reliance by establishing an infrastructure endowed with the capability to analyze the environment and understanding its context. Drawing from the classical semantic segmentation problem, our goal is to enable contextual comprehension of the environment, even in unfamiliar settings. Subsequently, a secondary analysis will ensue, culminating in the classification of the surrounding objects without reliance on external information, thereby accentuating adaptability.

Our aim is to distill pertinent environmental data into potential user objectives. Furthermore, we intend to leverage this infrastructure for the identification of obstacles or analogous elements that users may seek to avoid. This challenge aligns harmoniously with the framework of explainable AI, wherein algorithms are meticulously designed to not only deliver results but also furnish comprehensible explanations for their outcomes, tailored to human understanding.

Parallel to O1, we will also delve into the prospect of augmenting the quality of results through the incorporation of brain signals.

C. Objective O3: user in the loop

In Objective O3 (O3), our primary goal is to enhance the usability of human-robot collaboration facilitated by BMI devices. Whereas O1 and O2 focus on understanding the individual and the environment to provide suitable feedback to the robot, O3 concentrates on the effective delivery of feedback to the end user.

Extensive research underscores the pivotal role of precise feedback in stabilizing the brain signal and alleviating stress induced by an inaccurate decoder. Furthermore, we need to devise a means of incorporating the robot's perception without inundating the user with excessive information.

Our central hypothesis at this stage posits that, building upon the achievements of O1 and O2, slight adjustments to the output signal can facilitate direct presentation to the user. Moreover, O3 will encompass an evaluation of the overall process's robustness to ensure the project's safety for everyday use by end users.

D. Assessment

The project mandates an evaluation to verify the efficacy of human-robot cooperation in augmenting individual autonomy. In this context, we will devise experiments to rigorously assess the proposed solution across diverse user profiles and scenarios.

Initially, we will engage a cohort of at least ten healthy individuals to evaluate feasibility. Subsequently, we will transition to individuals with tetraplegia to validate the protocol's capabilities. The evaluation will encompass heterogeneous scenarios, commencing with classifier training and progressing to unfamiliar settings to scrutinize the adaptability of the controller.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Carlson and J. del R. Millan, "Brain-Controlled Wheelchairs: A Robotic Architecture," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 65–73, Mar. 2013.
- [2] J. del R. Millán et al., "Combining Brain–Computer Interfaces and Assistive Technologies: State-of-the-Art and Challenges," *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 4, 2010, Accessed: Mar. 08, 2023.
- [3] C. I. Penalzoza and S. Nishio, "BMI control of a third arm for multi-tasking," *Science Robotics*, vol. 3, no. 20, p. eaat1228, Jul. 2018.
- [4] S. Tortora, A. Gottardi, E. Menegatti, and L. Tonin, "Continuous Teleoperation of a Robotic Manipulator via Brain–Machine Interface with Shared Control," in *2022 IEEE 27th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, Stuttgart, Germany: IEEE Press, Oct. 2022.
- [5] L. Tonin and J. Millán, "Noninvasive brain–machine in-terfaces for robotic devices," *Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 191–214, 2021.
- [6] S. Tortora et al., "Neural correlates of user learning during long-term BCI training for the Cybathlon competition," *J NeuroEngineering Rehabil*, vol. 19, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Dec. 2022.
- [7] S. R. Soekadar, M. Witkowski, J. Mellinger, A. Ramos, N. Birbaumer and L. G. Cohen, "ERD-Based Online Brain–Machine Interfaces (BMI) in the Context of Neurorehabilitation: Optimizing BMI Learning and Performance," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 542–549, Oct. 2011.
- [8] C. H. Blabe, V. Gilja, C. A. Chestek, K. V. Shenoy, K. D. Anderson, and J. M. Henderson, "Assessment of brain–machine interfaces from the perspective of people with paralysis," *J. Neural Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 043002, Jul. 2015.